

Research Symposium: Student Encampments

Introduction: Genocidal Patriotism

Jodi Dean

*Jodi Dean is a professor in the Politics department at Hobart and William Smith Colleges in New York state. She is the author and editor of fourteen books including *Comrade: An Essay on Political Belonging* (Verso 2019). Email: jdean@hws.edu.*

When the *New York Times* editorial board declared that Kamala Harris is “the only patriotic choice for president” (New York Times 2024), I recalled a recent protest supporting Palestinian liberation. The protest was on public property, but close to a row of fraternity houses. The fraternity brothers responded to the chants from the small crowd of students, faculty, and community members by setting up speakers in their front lawn and blasting music to drown them out. The song of choice: the United States’ national anthem, sung repeatedly by patriotic brothers with hands over hearts. They expressed their patriotism by opposing those calling for an end to Israel’s genocidal war on Palestine.

Patriotism is typically associated with love and defense of one’s country, not with love and defense of another country. In 2024, U.S. patriotism has come to mean, among other things, defense of Israel no matter what. Support must be total and unconditional. One can criticize the United States and call it a racist, sexist, transphobic, militarist, carceral, settler-colonial state, but criticism of Israel is not allowed. The truth underpinning the association of U.S. patriotism with defense of Israel as it massacres Palestinian civilians is that Israel is using weapons supplied largely by the U.S. and acting with U.S. approval. The

genocide is overseen by the United States. It is held in place by U.S. aircraft carrier support groups in the Red Sea and targeting intelligence provided by officers in the U.S. Air Force (Petti and Klippenstein 2024). U.S. President Joe Biden identifies as a Zionist (Reuters 2023). Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu received 58 standing ovations when he spoke before a joint session of the U.S. Congress on July 24, 2024 (NPR 2024). At that time, the Israeli military with full U.S. backing had killed over 39,000 Palestinians in Gaza (Wafa News Agency 2024).

In his speech before Congress, Netanyahu criticized demonstrators gathered outside the Capitol, saying they were funded by Iran. He mocked campus protesters who chant “from the river to the sea,” saying,

Many don’t have a clue what river and what sea they’re talking about. They not only get an F in geography, they get an F in history. They call Israel a colonialist state. Don’t they know that the Land of Israel is where Abraham, Isaac and Jacob prayed, where Isaiah and Jeremiah preached and where David and Solomon ruled? (Times of Israel 2023).

In an odd move for the leader of a foreign government, Netanyahu praised patriotic

“fraternity brothers at the University of North Carolina who protected the American flag, protected the American flag against these anti-Israel protesters” (Times of Israel 2023).

Netanyahu’s remarks reiterated his condemnation of the wave of protests and encampments that spread across U.S. university campuses a few months earlier. In April 2024, he denounced the protests as horrific and unconscionable, products of antisemitic mobs calling for the annihilation of Israel and attacking Jewish faculty and students in ways reminiscent of German universities in the 1930s. Decrying the shameful response of university presidents and praising local, state, and federal officials, Netanyahu insisted that more had to be done and not simply because “they want to kill Jews where ever they are, that’s bad enough” but because they say “death to America” (NBC News 2023).

Taken literally, Netanyahu’s remarks are simply false. The campus protests universally called for a ceasefire. Many combined these calls with their long-standing advocacy of divestment from and boycotting of companies profiting from Israel’s occupation of Palestinian territory. Nearly all the encampments were diverse, inclusive, and ecumenical. Students invited one another to participate in their religious and cultural traditions. They learned from and protected each other, creating the safe spaces that the neoliberal university promised but consistently failed to provide. The protests and encampments didn’t express a desire to kill. They aimed to protect life, including Palestinian life.

Netanyahu’s words are not meant to be taken literally. His interventions in the heated culture wars on U.S. university campuses are intended to reinforce the identification of U.S. interests with Israeli interests. In his

view, attacks on Israel are attacks on America, and defending Israel equates to defending America. The two are as one and the same. The culture war achievement here is that patriotic U.S. citizens, often and aspirationally white, now have a minoritized identity. They, too, are victims entitled to special protections. Because anti-zionism has been defined as antisemitism, Zionism is treated as more than a political position or ideology in a larger battle of ideas. It is an identity, the criticism of which is potentially discriminatory. White Anglo-Saxon Protestant fraternity brothers can claim that Jewish defenders of Palestine are subjecting them to antisemitic bigotry and harassment, making them unsafe. They are as much in need of a safe space as any raced or sexed minority.

From what is Israel protecting the U.S.? Netanyahu’s words suggest that support for Israel is a defense against anti-Americanism, against those who would criticize the U.S., who would call it a racist, sexist, transphobic, militarist, carceral, settler-colonial state, who would disrupt the serenity of campus life with political demonstrations, who would burn flags. Support for Israel provides those patriots offended by such speech and action with a way to fight back, on the very terrain of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion that they find so egregious. Antony Lerman writes: “Israel now symbolizes the fate of the West, however the West might be defined – which today can be as much about the values a country objects to as about values it shares with others” (Lerman 2022, 206). Lerman is discussing how Israel came to be more European than the Europeans, an ethno-nationalist bulwark against Arabs and Muslims. The opposition to pro-Palestinian demonstrations on U.S. university campuses shows how Israel has become more U.S. than the U.S., emblematic of the will to defend a stronghold against

those who would use inclusion and tolerance to undermine it.

The strategy has been effective. University administrations have jettisoned fundamental features of higher education: critical inquiry, free expression, and political engagement. Some institutions appear to be targeting particular students, such as the Black British Muslim Cornell graduate student Momodou Taal (Nathanson 2024). Cornell suspended Taal for participating in a protest against weapons contractors at a campus job fair. The university informed him that since his F-1 visa would be revoked, he should prepare for deportation.

Given the neoliberal institutional shifts toward reliance on contingent faculty, the price for telling the truth and speaking out against occupation and genocide is largely borne by those without the security of tenure. But tenure itself offers no guarantee; it is only as good as one's lawyer, if one can afford it or can find one among the already overwhelmed number of lawyers working pro-bono to defend the defenders of Palestine. Even administrators aren't safe: from the university presidents fired or forced to resign (U Penn, Harvard, Columbia) to the deans making critical remarks in private text messages (Columbia).

Some might attribute academia's McCarthyite atmosphere to the Department of Education Office of Civil Rights' amped up use of Title VI prohibitions against discrimination based on religion and shared ancestry. But its 'Dear Colleague letter' from May 2024 emphasized that nothing in its instructions should be construed as authorizing the restriction of First Amendment rights. Others might blame overzealous college presidents pressured by influential donors. This line of argument

risks being accused of employing an antisemitic trope, despite the fact that billionaire donors deeply committed to Jewish philanthropy have publicly condemned university presidents for tolerating demonstrations of solidarity with Palestine and urged others to withhold donations (Jerusalem Post 2024; Gross 2024; Harvard Crimson 2023).

While there is no single cause, faculty themselves bear some responsibility for acquiescing to the decades of silencing their colleagues teaching and researching Palestine have endured. Tenured faculty looked the other way when contingent faculty were surveilled and harassed for Palestinian content. They failed to defend the academic freedom of Palestinian and Israeli scholars telling the truth about the Nakba, occupation, and apartheid or join them in supporting the Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement. Strangely and unconscionably, some faculty actively undercut students protesting genocide, criticizing their slogans for lack of nuance, as if they were ignorant of the slogan form. Naively and misguidedly, some of us embraced the myth that education requires being immunized from conflict and shielded from the outside world, as if learning was easy and the university was not a porous institution within a divided world.

This past spring, many of us were heartened by the demonstrations of faculty in solidarity with their students, especially by those who put their bodies on the line. Yet, this fall too, many of us are censoring ourselves, accepting the draconian anti-protest policies implemented over the summer. We hope for a return to normalcy, unaware that this is it – unless we fight for something else. ♦

References

Devereaux, Ryan. 2024. "Israel's Air Force Targeting of Gaza Relies on Vast Intelligence Gathering Operation." *The Intercept*, January 11, 2024. <https://theintercept.com/2024/01/11/israel-air-force-targeting-intelligence/> (October 3, 2024).

eJewish Philanthropy. 2024. "Marc Rowan: It's Time to 'Exact a Price' for Antisemitism." *eJewishPhilanthropy*. <https://ejewishphilanthropy.com/marc-rowan-its-time-to-exact-a-price-for-antisemitism/> (October 3, 2024).

Gross, Judah Ari. 2024. "Marc Rowan: It's Time to 'Exact a Price' for Antisemitism." *eJewishPhilanthropy*. <https://ejewishphilanthropy.com/marc-rowan-its-time-to-exact-a-price-for-antisemitism/> (October 3, 2024).

Harvard Crimson. 2023. "Blavatnik Halts Donations to Universities Over Antisemitism." *Harvard Crimson*, December 22, 2023. <https://www.thecrimson.com/article/2023/12/22/blavatnik-halts-donations-antisemitism/> (October 3, 2024).

Jerusalem Post. 2024. "50 Most Influential Jews of 2024." *Jerusalem Post*, October 3, 2024. <https://www.jpost.com/influencers-24/50jews-24/article-822163>.

Lerman, Antony. 2022. *Whatever Happened to Anti-Semitism?* London: Pluto Press.

Mason, Jeff, and Patricia Zengerle. 2023. "‘I Am a Zionist’: How Joe Biden’s Lifelong Bond with Israel Shapes War Policy." *Reuters*, October 21, 2023. <https://www.reuters.com/world/us/i-am-zionist-how-joe-bidens-lifelong-bond-with-israel-shapes-war-policy-2023-10-21/> (October 3, 2024).

NBC News. 2023. "Netanyahu Denounces U.S. College Campus Protests as Antisemitic." *NBC News*, October 2, 2023. <https://www.nbcnews.com/video/netanyahu-denounces-u-s-college-campus-protests-as-antisemitic-209638981991> (October 3, 2024).

New York Times. 2024. "Opinion | Kamala Harris and the 2024 Race." *New York Times*, September 30, 2024. <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/09/30/opinion/editorials/kamala-harris-2024.html> (October 3, 2024).

Times of Israel. 2023. "Full Text of Netanyahu's Address to Congress: 'We're Protecting You.'" *Times of Israel*, October 22, 2023. <https://www.timesofisrael.com/were-protecting-you-full-text-of-netanyahus-address-to-congress/> (October 3, 2024).

Wafa News Agency. 2024. "Gaza death toll from Israel's deadly aggression surpasses 39,145," July 24, 2024. <https://english.wafa.ps/Pages/Details/147329> (October 3, 2024).